

Title: Everything you need to know about the luxury access platform for "crypto-affluents"

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INTRODUCTION:

You coined the term "crypto-affluents". Can you define better who they are, and what potential they represent for luxury merchants?

The total market capitalisation of all crypto-currencies have increased from USD 12 billion just 12 months ago, to USD 200 billion today. It is probably the best performing asset class in the last 2 years. This huge increase has minted a significant new group of affluent people who hold a lot of their new wealth in crypto-currencies.

Contrary to popular opinion, not all crypto-affluent are programmers! The space is extremely vibrant and fast-moving and has drawn many new participants from bankers to professionals etc. And there are many different ways in which crypto-affluents created their crypto-wealth, from holding to trading to ICOs.

What is clear is that with the continued influx of capital into crypto-currencies, crypto-currency values and the numbers of crypto-affluents will continue to increase. This is a new community of possible customers luxury merchants simply cannot afford to ignore.

BIOGRAPHY:

Aditus co-founder Julian Peh discusses how luxury merchants can reach out to this new community of customers.

Julian Peh has a 15-year history of developing and launching luxury marketing platforms that include websites, apps, and rewards programmes. He previously founded and built Luxury Insider, which turned into one of the leading luxury portals in Asia before it was acquired by Singapore Press Holdings. He has also been co-founder and CEO of SERA, a rewards programme which has acquired rewards from over 100 luxury brand stores so far.

Amidst the growing interest towards blockchain technology, Peh co-founded Aditus, a decentralised luxury marketing platform for merchants to so-called "crypto-affluents." The platform allows customers to access Smart Invitations for products that are personalised and private but still targeted towards them. Through Aditus, clients can also access rewards programmes previously only available for credit card holders.

In an exclusive interview with Singapore Business Review, Peh talks about how blockchain technology can be used to bridge gaps between luxury merchants and those wealthy with crypto assets. He also shares how security developments are improving the way luxury technology is being made and used.